

COMMUNICATIVE PRINCIPLES OF SPEECH CULTURE

A.B. Murtazaeva

Teacher: Uzbekistan state world languages university

Department: Philology "Practical aspects of the English language"

Tel:(90)935-81-27 aisafar81@mail.ru

<https://www.doi.org/10.37547/ejsspc-v03-i02-p2-73>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 16th February 2023

Accepted: 26th February 2023

Online: 27th February 2023

KEY WORDS

Communicative qualities,
speech correctness, accuracy,
logic, purity, richness,
appropriateness,
expressiveness, impressiveness,
cultural speech, speech
technology.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the communicative principles of speech culture, certain communicative tasks in the process of speech construction and comprehension, and the correlation with external structures related to it.

Introduction

Communicativeness in speech culture is related to the ability to make a correct and meaningful speech. The first views in this regard belong to Aristotle. Recognizing oratory as an art, he created the doctrine of the qualities of speech by summarizing the previously created theory and observations. This doctrine rests mainly on the principle of intelligibility. "The most important achievement in verbal expression is to be intelligible," says Aristotle in the Poetics. He also recognizes that the necessary qualities of a good speech - correctness, accuracy, appropriateness, universality, pleasantness to the ear, purity, etc. - are subject to intelligibility and lead to its maximum manifestation.

His ideas were later developed in Ancient Rome. According to the Romans, a good speech should be short, elegant, fluent, confident, uplifting, solemn, wide-ranging, bright, lively, warm, simple, truthful. All the thinkers of the ancient world recognized the qualities of comprehensibility, correctness, appropriateness, purity, clarity and elegance as the main characteristics of a good speech.

The quality of intelligibility, which is manifested on the basis of the form and content of the speech, is also of fundamental and decisive importance for this research. Such qualities characteristic of a good speech are also reflected in works on the art of oratory created in the 15th-17th centuries. For example, in "Rhetoric", which appeared in Russia in 1620, the purity, beauty, clarity, and comprehensibility of speech were recognized, while in the era of Peter I, comprehensibility, staying within the bounds of decency, beauty, decoration, rational use of pictorial and artistic decorations, fluency, harmony, logicity were noted. done Later, M. views in this field. V. enriched by Lomonosov.

Analyze of referenced literatures

In 1980 B. I. Golovin's training manual for the course "Basics of speech culture" fully describes the characteristics of a good speech. The scientist said that "in the process of constructing speech and understanding it, certain communicative tasks are solved and gain a balance with the external structures associated with it."

Communicative signs and qualities of speech are appropriate and specific to non-speech components, which facilitate the communication process. Communicative sign characteristic of any speech B. N. It is justified by Golovin through its correlation with some component of the communicative act. For example, the ratio "speech - addressee" ensures universality and impact of speech. The quality of appropriateness is manifested on the basis of "speech - communication conditions" relations. The ratio of "speech - thinking", "speech - being" makes it possible to understand the clarity and logic of speech. The connection "speech - consciousness" helps to understand the communicative features of speech, such as expressiveness, imagery, appropriateness, effectiveness.

The relationship between "speech and literary language" makes it possible to think about the purity of speech. V. N. Golovin combines it into a system consisting of "communicative stages". Disturbances in the relationship of speech with non-speech components lead to a violation of the quality of speech at any communicative stage.

In V. N. Golovin's teaching, the system of communicative qualities of speech is made up of correctness, accuracy, logicity, expressiveness, imagery, purity, appropriateness, comprehensibility, universality and impressiveness. According to Golovin, correctness is such a communicative sign that "without it, others cannot be used."

The strongest point of V. N. Golovin's teaching is that it reflects the modern demand - communicativeness. However, some researchers point out that the special linguistic knowledge of the language owner is disconnected from everyday speech practice as its weak point.

The content of communicative qualities has not been clarified until the end. V. N. According to Golovin, to speak in simple language is to speak clearly, clearly and truthfully.

R. Kongurov and E. Among the communicative qualities of speech, Begmatov points out the cases of correctness, purity, accuracy, logic, impressiveness, imagery, comprehensibility and appropriateness of speech.

"Any quality of speech is evaluated as a mistake or deficiency of speech, which is determined by how much (positively or negatively) it affects the effectiveness of the text and speech in a certain genre and style," he says.

Research methodology

Correctness of speech. Correct speech is to follow the standards of modern literary language. Correctness of speech from qualities of cultured speech. Other qualities of speech culture:

1. Clarity of speech is considered one of its most important qualities.

There are 2 types of speech clarity.

- Subject accuracy
- Conceptual clarity

Object precision is based on the relationship between speech and reality. While giving a speech, the speaker must know the subject of the speech clearly: he must know well all the signs of this subject, its various aspects, which subject is related to which subject. Analyzing the story "Death of a Hero" by A. Qakhkhor Ma'ruf Hakim, he cites the following passage: "Batir strapped five bombs to his waist and ran into the street with a bomb in his hand." It is clear from this passage that the author does not distinguish between a bomb and a grenade. A single ambiguity can detract from the value of a work of art. Every teacher should know the subject he/she is teaching, every journalist should know the article he/she is writing, and the scientist should know the subject of his/her research.

L.N. Tolstoy said: "A word is an expression of thought." The word should be proportionate to the thought being expressed. "It is necessary to speak in such a way that people have a clear idea of what they express in every thought."

Conceptual accuracy is closely related to synonyms, polysemous words, expressions and a good perception of each meaning. In order to ensure the quality of speech accuracy, the following conditions must be met:

- 1) good knowledge of the subject of speech. This is an extralinguistic factor, and every journalist should have a clear idea of the subject of speech in the article he writes.
- 2) good knowledge of the language system. Communicate in accordance with grammatical, lexical, phonetic, and stylistic standards.
- 3) strong speaking skills. Communication skills are always required.

2. Expressiveness of speech

Expressiveness is the quality of speech that regularly holds the attention and interest of the listener or reader. There are different forms of expressiveness.

These are definitely used in different conversations. Of course, these should be used in appropriate situations.

The bases of expression are as follows:

- Communication situation

The expressiveness of a teacher's speech differs from that of a political speaker. The expressiveness of a diplomat's, judge's, lawyer's speech.

- The structural side of the language.

This includes pronunciation, word, morphological, syntactic intonation and stylistic expression. So, expressiveness is manifested through units of language levels.

Conditions that ensure expressiveness of speech:

1. Thinking, independence of thinking.
2. Systematically and consciously develop speech skills.
3. Not to be indifferent to the spoken speech.
4. Good knowledge of the possibilities of the language.
5. Providing a mental foundation for expressiveness: the tools that ensure expressiveness are words, different sounds, and intonation.

3. Logic of speech

Logicity has a commonality with correctness and accuracy, because a grammatically distorted, misleading lexical unit also leads to a violation of logic. For example, if the word went to the school is not used in the combination, the word went to the school becomes

meaningless. The concept of the word "we held the meeting" in the combination "we held the meeting" leads to a lack of accuracy and a violation of logic.

There are two types of logic:

1. *Object and object logic;*
2. *The logic of the concept.*

When something is said to be logical, the correspondence of expressiveness is behind the linguistic units of events and events. In reality, things and events are logically connected. This relationship should be clearly indicated through language elements. But in fairy tales, fiction and other artistic creations, this feature can be violated: resurrection of the dead, flying soup, and various magical actions.

Conceptual logic is the logical continuation of an idea through language elements. M: now relax by listening to tunes and dances (from the radio), the logic of the concept is broken.

Incorrect translations also destroy the logic of speech: The price of men's socks has been reduced by 10 percent (translation of "mujskie noski").

2. Purity of speech

In this case, it is understood that the speech corresponds to the literary norm. The elements that destroy the purity of speech are: dialectism, barbarism, slang. If dialect words are not used properly, the purity of the speech will be disturbed. Nowadays, it is observed that journalists speak in dialect in their speeches on radio and television, use rude words: tak, khosh innaykigin, so, that is, etc. Use of other language words: voobshe, problema em - hayshak issue, theme, style ... etc.

4. Appropriateness of speech

Appropriateness is such a quality of speech that it corresponds to all conditions and goals of communication. An appropriate speech corresponds to the topic of the conversation, meets its logical and emotional content, audience, content, reporting function, educational and aesthetic requirements.

Appropriateness is such a feature that if it is not there, speech features such as clarity and logic will lose their appropriateness. Appropriateness is a task-related quality, which is based on the appropriateness of speech, therefore, appropriateness means the appropriateness of language means to the purpose of speech.

So, based on the above, the appropriateness of speech can be divided into the following types:

1. Methodological relevance
2. Contextual appropriateness
3. Appropriateness of circumstances
4. Personal-psychological appropriateness.

5. Richness and color of speech

The richness of the speech means the use of words and expressions that value it. Evaluative words: artistic images, expressions, proverbs and proverbs, wise words, excerpts from works of art. When speaking about the richness of speech, the first idea is that it is understood how many language units are used in the speech field, which have different meanings. The more words and phrases that are not repeated in the speech, the richer the speech, the less the poor speech. Presentations of speech richness:

1. Lexicon - vocabulary
2. Semantic vocabulary

Lexical vocabulary of an educated modern person is 10-12 thousand words. Pushkin's vocabulary consists of 21,000 units.

Semantic wealth means the ability to connect one word with another word. M: queen of the field, queen of the forest, queen of her daughters, queen of my heart, queen of the group, etc. It is impossible to match 5 different words.

Conclusion. Cultivation of speech culture is not only educational work in the field of philology, but also one of the most important aspects of ideological, political and educational work. That is why studying this subject is an essential need for future professionals. This need is realized by learning the secrets of the art of speaking, speaking and writing correctly in accordance with the standards of the literary language, learning the art of using lexical and grammatical units of the language appropriately and appropriately. Nevertheless, it is desirable to increase the weight and number of textbooks and training manuals that can satisfy such needs and requirements.

References:

1. Gudratov T. Fundamentals of speech culture. - Tashkent: Teacher, 1993.
2. Begmatov E., Mamatov A. Theory of literary norm. Parts 1-2-3.- Tashkent, 1997, 1998, 2000.
3. Artykov A. Speech culture and the art of oratory. Tashkent, 2002. 6.
4. Tojiev Yo., Hasanova J., Tojimatov H., Yoldosheva O. Basics of Uzbek speech culture and methodology. - Tashkent, 1994, 2006.
5. Mahmudov N. Teacher speech culture. -T: Alisher Navoi National Library, 2007.